

1 **Morphological and compositional analysis of alluvial gold: The Fresnedoso gold placer**
2 **(Spain)**

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18

19 The Fresnedoso creek gold placer (FGP) in the Moraleja Basin (W Iberian Massif) has been investigated in terms
20 of morphological, textural and compositional evolution of gold particles. A mixture of two populations has been
21 identified being coherent with primary sources located at a proximal (2.5-10 km), and distal (20-50 km) range.
22 Shape and compositional evidences suggest recycling of paleoplacers (tertiary) has to be considered to some
23 extend. Primary laminar morphologies point to lode deposits in small-flat veins hosted in the metasediments of the
24 Schist Greywacke Complex. All these features suggest the Fresnedoso creek gold placer is a deposit constituted
25 by with mono- and polycyclic particles. Transport distance – Flattening indexes (CFI, Shilo) models have been
26 tested and result in useful information for exploration of undiscovered deposits, even with a limited dataset.
27 Compositional analysis of gold particle morphotypes has revealed that the Fresnedoso gold is a AuAg bimetallic
28 alloy. Textural and compositional groups include: type 1 (Au1= Au₈₉₋₉₄Ag₁₁₋₆), type 2 (Au2= Au₉₉Ag₁) and type
29 3 (Au3~ Au >99). Variations in composition of type 1 (Particle's cores) could reflect differences in primary
30 composition, spatial dispersion of sources or secondary processes, but fit within the compositional range of
31 orogenic gold deposits. Secondary processes have been explored to explain compositional heterogeneity in the
32 particles. Gold type 2 (rim) and 3 (micro-aggregates) represents two different de-alloying stages, from initial Ag-
33 leaching at the rim and/or through grain-boundaries and microfractures (Au2), to complete resetting of primary
34 chemical imprint, pervasive porous texture and Au re-precipitation with Fe-OOH and clays (Au3). A model is
35 proposed which combines: Ag de-alloying enhanced in a Cl-Fe rich environment (lateritic) and the
36 deformation/recrystallization processes related to mechanical cold-work in the river load-bed during transport.

37

38 **Keywords:** Gold placer, Orogenic gold deposits, morphological analysis, laterite, Moraleja Cenozoic
39 basin, Iberian Massif

40

41 **1. INTRODUCTION**

42

43 Historically alluvial deposits have been important sources of gold worldwide (Garnett and
44 Bassett, 2005; Mudaliar et al., 2007; Kerr et al., 2017; Rivas et al., 2017). Placer gold deposits are the
45 result of the erosion of primary sources or/and the recycling of previous detrital deposits, and the
46 subsequent deposition in different sedimentary environments (Garnett and Bassett, 2005; Mudaliar et
47 al., 2007; Kerr et al., 2017; Rivas et al., 2017). Hydrothermal fluids interacting with rocks commonly
48 form primary gold deposits (e.g. Gaboury, 2019). Weathering and erosion of those systems, liberates
49 detrital gold particles that suffer physicochemical transformations downstream (Knight et al., 1999a and
50 b; Johnson and McQueen, 2001; Garnett and Bassett, 2005). Mechanical contrast between soft gold
51 particles and silicates in fluvial flows, results into a strong modification of gold shape and microstructure
52 (e.g. Hérail et al., 1990; Youngson and Craw, 1999; Townley et al., 2003; Stewart et al., 2017).

53

54 A correlation has been proposed between gold particle morphological parameters and fluvial
55 dynamics and transport distance, in an attempt to constraint the location and style of primary deposits
56 sourcing placers (e.g. Corey, 1949; Cailleux and Tricart, 1959; Tishchenko and Tishchenko, 1974;
57 Tishchenko, 1981; Shilo, 1985; Groen et al., 1990; Herail et al., 1990, Youngson and Craw, 1993, 1995;
58 Eyles, 1995; Knight et al., 1999a; Youngson and Craw, 1999; Wierchowiec, 2002; Dill et al., 2009;
59 Barrios et al., 2015). However, the specific behaviour of gold particles during fluvial transport is
60 incomplete, because the number of morphological studies in well-constrained natural systems is low,
61 and the mechanical interaction of gold within the bead-load is poorly understood (e.g. Shilo and
62 Shumilov, 1970; Knight et al., 1994; Youngson and Craw, 1999; Barrios et al., 2015).

63

64 Besides, alluvial gold particles around the world frequently develop a chemical zoning with a
65 rim close to pure Au and inner levels with higher Ag contents (Desborough, 1970; Groen et al., 1990;
66 Youngson and Craw, 1993; Knight et al., 1999a; Chapman et al., 2000a and b; Wierchowiec, 2002;
67 Chapman et al., 2011; Chapman and Mortensen, 2016; Stewart et al., 2017). The origin of the chemical
68 zoning is a subject of debate. Several refining mechanisms have been proposed like Ag-leaching
69 (Desborough, 1970) and dissolution-precipitation (bio-) processes (Youngson and Craw, 1993; Groen
70 et al., 1990; Falconer and Craw, 2009; Reith et al., 2012; Fairbrother et al., 2012; Rea et al., 2019).
71 Stewart et al. (2017) suggest that recrystallization of gold rims could play a role in Ag-leaching.
72 Notwithstanding chemical composition of gold particles could be useful to link placer deposits to
73 primary sources and identify recycling processes (Mosier et al., 1989; Leake et al., 1998; Chapman et
74 al., 2000a), some evidences indicate that primary geochemical footprint is diluted with transport distance
75 (10 – 20 km range) and/or recrystallization (e.g. Knight et al., 1999a; Chapman and Mortensen, 2016;
76 Stewart et al., 2017).

77

78 Lode and placers gold deposits have long been known in the Iberian Massif (Spain) (e.g. Lewis
79 and Jones, 1970; Spiering et al., 2000; Vázquez Calvo et al., 2013; Barrios, 2014). In particular, the
80 Southern part of the Iberian Massif presents abundant evidence of gold deposits, including the
81 occurrence of large gold nuggets (218 g). Nevertheless, morphological and chemical studies of gold are
82 very limited, and primary sources of many placers remain unsolved (e.g. Barrios 2014; Barrios et al.,
83 2015). The present work deals with the morphological and chemical analysis, of the Quaternary
84 Fresnedoso creek placer deposit, developed in the NE area of Cenozoic Ponsul-Moraleja basin (Western
85 Central Iberia, Spain; Friend and Dabrio, 1996; de Vicente et al., 2007, 2018). The Fresnedoso gold
86 placer (FGP) represents an excellent example of alluvial gold deposit developed in Cenozoic basins of
87 Iberia, following the dismantling of the basement reliefs to the present times (Barrios, 2014). The FGP
88 primary source is unknown but the presence of lode deposits in the region provides an important
89 constraint to test transport/morphological models in the area (e.g. Knight et al., 1999a). Primary and
90 secondary processes could leave their chemical imprint in gold particles. Combining both morphological
91 and chemical analysis of alluvial gold we will constrain the genetic and sedimentary evolution of the
92 particles, as a starting point to develop a regional exploration model to discover new deposits.

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95 **2. GEOLOGICAL CONTEXT**

96

97 The Fresnedoso creek gold placer (FGP) is located at the NE end of the late Cenozoic Ponsul-Moraleja
98 basin (PM; Fig. 1), formed as part of piedmonts of the Spanish-Portuguese Central System (SPCS). The
99 SPCS is a prominent relief generated by a thick-skinned crustal pop-up related to and overall N-S
100 tectonic shortening during the Cenozoic (Santanach, 1994; Friend and Dabrio, 1996, Barsó et al., 2003;
101 de Vicente et al., 2007, 2018; Cunha et al., 2019). The basin has a NE-SW trend and is bordered to the
102 North by Variscan basement relief (Fig. 1). The northern boundary of the PM basin is a complex fault
103 zone which includes a general south-verging thrust activity, with lateral segments showing significant
104 sinistral strike-slip component, the Ponsul-Gata thrust (POG; Fig. 1).

105

106 The Variscan basement in the area is part of the Central Iberian Zone (CIZ; Julivert et al., 1972),
107 in the Iberian Massif. The low-grade Neoproterozoic materials from the Schist-Greywacke Complex
108 (SGC), consists of a very thick metasedimentary sequence of Neoproterozoic to lower Cambrian age,
109 with shales, sandstones and minor conglomerate and volcanoclastic beds (Díez Balda et al., 1990;
110 Rodríguez Alonso et al., 2004). Spotted slates and phyllites with andalusite and cordierite, result from
111 contact metamorphism to the North of Ponsul-Gata thrust (Fig. 1). Variscan deformation is polyphasic
112 and results from the collision of Laurussia and Gondwana during the Late Paleozoic (Azor et al., 2019).
113 The regional structure corresponds to compressional structures (C1 phase, Azor et al., 2019), with large

114 subvertical folds oriented ESE-WNW (e.g. Cañaveral syncline, Fig 1) associated with an schistosity
115 (S1). Abundant syn- to post-tectonic granitoids intruded the Variscan Iberian massif (Días et al., 1998;
116 Castro et al., 2002; Villaseca et al., 2012). The Jálama pluton is an epizonal zoned peraluminous
117 granitoid of the monzogranitic suite (S₂-type; Pesquera et al., 2018; Roda-Robles et al., 2018). It is a
118 late-tectonic intrusion with transitional affinities (Calc-alkaline contaminated granites, Castro, 2019).
119 The Santibáñez pluton corresponds to a two-mica synkinematic granitoid (Anatectic granites; Castro,
120 2019).

121

122 The sedimentary infill of the Ponsul-Moraleja basin in this area includes Paleogene and Neogene
123 continental deposits (De Vicente et al., 2018; Cunha et al., 2019). Paleogene crops out in the lower part
124 of the PM basin (sandstones, arkoses and mudstones), shows alluvial, lacustrine and channel-fill
125 sedimentary features (Bascones Alvira et al., 1987). It has been proposed a regional correlation of these
126 deposits with UBS6, 7, 8 and 9 allostratigraphic units (UBS: unconformity-bounded sequences; De
127 Vicente et al., 2018; Cunha et al., 2019). Neogene deposits include alluvial-fan deposits: a) Miocene
128 sequences with heterometric conglomerates with a clay matrix, comprising clasts of slate and
129 metagreywackes (with accessory quartz clasts), sandstone, arkosic sandstones and mudstones (Bascones
130 Alvira et al., 1987), and b) Pliocene sediments including conglomerates (quartzite clasts and red clay
131 matrix), sandstones and clays, limited to the W area of the basin (Fig. 1). Neogene sequences have been
132 correlated with UBS11-12 and UBS13 respectively (De Vicente et al., 2018; Cunha et al., 2019)
133 Pliocene Alluvial-fan deposits (Conglomerates, sandstones and mudstones) in the upper part. A
134 correlation has been proposed for these Miocene and Pliocene sequences with allostratigraphic units.
135 Undifferentiated lower Quaternary deposits include terraces and flood plains (sands, clays and rounded
136 quartzitic clasts) (Bascones Alvira et al., 1987). Quaternary alluvial deposits in the present river network
137 include sands, clays and gravels (clasts of schists, phyllites, granitoids and quartz).

138

139 Gold placers are known in the area where similar gold deposits have already been targets of
140 Roman mining, such as Sierro de Corria or Sierro de Marifranca, both of which are located in the Coria
141 Basin (Florido et al., 2007; Rivas et al., 2008). Artisan mining works in the Fresnedoso creek gold placer
142 (FGP) started about XIX century. Preliminary analyses to evaluate possible reserves in the FGP of Sn,
143 W and Au, and more recently Ta and Ti, estimated contents of 0.095 g/t for Au and 91 g/t for Sn (IGME,
144 1982). Besides the close spatial relationship of the FGP deposit and the POG fault system makes the
145 particle analyses a potential source of information about the tectonic activity of the Ponsul-Moraleja
146 basin.

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149 3. METHODOLOGY

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151 3.1. Sampling collection and preparation

152

153 The gold particles were sampled along the Fresnedoso creek (Fig. 1) sediments, which include a mixture
154 of gravel (30% slate/schist, 10% granitoid and 20% quartz 2% diabase clasts) and a matrix of sand (20%)
155 and grey/red clays (18%). A 127 x 23 x 25 cm sluice box (Royal Manufacturing ©) with 8 flat rifles,
156 were used to wash 4.2 m³ of sediment along 700 m of the Fresnedoso creek. Subsequently, the recovered
157 aggregate were concentrated with a 40 cm diameter pan and eventually cleaned in ultrasonic bath.
158 Coarse magnetic fraction was removed from the concentrate using a neodymium magnet. 310 gold
159 particles were handpicked under a binocular microscope.

160

161 3.2. Morphotextural analysis

162

163 Digital images of gold particles were collected with a Leica MZ6 binocular microscope with a
164 HD camera. In order to manipulate small fractions, particles were placed on microscope glass-plates
165 with double-sided tape. Images were processed with ImageJ software (Schindelin et al., 2012) to obtain
166 particle dimensions: length (L), which corresponds to the largest axis, Width (W), which corresponds to
167 the largest axis perpendicular to (L), and thickness (T) (Fig. 2). This method has been tested in previous
168 morphological research (e.g. Crawford and Mortensen, 2009).

169

170

171 3.3. Faulting and drainage network analysis

172

173 Regional orientation of both faulting and drainage patterns were evaluated in the area. Fault patterns
174 were manually digitized from the 1:50000 geologic cartographic databases of the Spanish Geological
175 Survey (IGME; <http://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/Magna50.aspx>) and photointerpretation
176 of aerial and satellite images. Simplified drainage network was obtained from the Confederación
177 Hidrográfica del Tajo geographical database (<http://www.chtajo.es/>). Binary images were analyzed with
178 the intercepts method as implemented in the software SPO2003 (Launeau and Robin, 1996), selecting
179 an angular step of 5°. A linear filter of 10 was used to reduce the effects of grid anisotropy on the
180 counting of intercepts. As a result a rose of directions is obtained (Figs. 1 and 17).

181

182 Particle dimensions were used for the calculation of the Cailleux and Corey form indices, widely
183 used in the literature (e.g. Eyles, 1995; Knight et al., 1999a; Youngson and Craw, 1999; Wierchowiec,
184 2002; Townley et al., 2003; Rasmussen et al., 2006; Barrios et al., 2015), as well as several parameters:
185 the equivalent sphere diameter ($ESD = (LWT)^{1/3}$), and its 2D counterpart the equivalent circle diameter
186 ($ECD = \sqrt{LW}$), and the Aspect ratio (L/T) (e.g. Bonev et al., 2002; Barrios et al., 2015).

187

188 Cailleux's flattening index ($CFI = (L+W) / 2T$) quantifies mass redistribution in a malleable
189 particle due to blows and bends suffered during its transport in fluvial environments (Cailleux and
190 Tricart, 1959). The Shilo flattening index is also common in the literature; here will be used punctually
191 following the classical formulation $Shilo = [(L+W)/2T]-1$ (Shilo and Shumilov, 1970). The Corey Shape
192 factor ($CSF = T / \sqrt{LW}$), numerically describes the level of flatness of a particle, where values closer to
193 0 are associated with planar particles and values closer to 1 indicate more spherical shapes (Corey,
194 1949). The equivalent sphere diameter gives a unique value related to particle size from the diameter of
195 a sphere enclosed in a cube with dimensions equivalent to the three main dimensional axes of the particle
196 (Jennings and Parslow, 1988). When only two dimensions of the particle are available, the equivalent
197 circle diameter is descriptor (Bonev et al., 2002; Barrios et al., 2015). Aspect ratio (AR) is a two-
198 dimensional parameter that relates the longest and shortest particle dimensions, being useful to describe
199 the elongation of the particle (Gómez Barreiro and Martínez Catalán, 2012; Bonev et al., 2002; Barrios
200 et al., 2015). The particle shape was classified according to the mathematical diagram of Zingg (1935);
201 and morphologically according to their roundness (rounded, intermediate roundness and angular
202 roundness) and sphericity (discoidal, subdiscoidal, spheroidal and elongated), according to the visual
203 diagram of Barrios et al. (2015), adapted from Powers (1982). Statistical analysis of morphological data
204 was conducted on R version 3.5.3 (R Core Team, 2019). Based on these results, an analysis of particle
205 population mixing was performed by Gaussian finite mixture modelling (mclust package; Scrucca
206 2017).

207

208 Surface analyses were conducted on representative morphotypes with scanning electron
209 microscopy (SEM) to identify morphological features such as crystallization textures, associated
210 minerals and transport marks/features (Barrios et al., 2015). Particles were then mounted in epoxy and
211 polished to conduct microchemical and microstructural study. Mineral inclusions and textural zoning
212 were first evaluated using a Nikon Model H550S Reflected Light Optical Microscope. Chemical
213 mapping was done with energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) with a microscope JEOL JSM-
214 6010PLUS / LA 20 kV. Quantitative electron microprobe (EMPA) analyses were conducted in the same
215 samples in a JEOL JXA-8900M (beam size: 5 μ m; 20 kV; ZAF correction routine).

216

217

218 4. RESULTS

219

220 4.1. Surface analysis

221

222 Gold is malleable and a very soft material in contrast to most silicates and rock fragments
223 transported by a river. Variation on the Ag/Au ratio increases gold hardness with the Ag content, but it
224 seems to have a no significant impact on morphological evolution of gold particles (e.g. Wrighton,
225 2013). The surface of our particles has obvious transport marks. Observed under the SEM, a collection
226 of features appeared, with irregular and rounded morphologies, rough surfaces, scratch marks and
227 depressions generated by blows and abrasion (Fig. 3 C and D). Some particles have positive and negative
228 planar surfaces, that could be interpreted, respectively, as gold crystal faces or molds left by minerals
229 that were adhered (e.g. quartz) and eventually disaggregated by transport (Fig. 3 E and F). The irregular
230 and lobular morphologies, known as spongiform particles are common (Fig. 3 A-C; Davies et al., 1989;
231 Santosh and Omana, 1991; Craw, 1992; Krupp and Weiser, 1992; Eyles, 1995; Kalinin et al., 2009;
232 Reith et al., 2009). In some particle a penetrative porous surface has been identified (Figs. 4 A and B).
233 Remains of filonian quartz are rarely preserved in gold particles (Fig. 4 C).

234

235 The 30% of particles have hammering marks (Fig. 5 A and D), from which a 33% depicted
236 severe blow damage (e.g. fractures) (Fig. 5 A, C and D), and in other 30% particles are folded (Fig. 5
237 A, B, C, D, E and F). Hammering is the main cause of shape change in fluvial transported gold particles,
238 being related to particle thinning processes. In contrast, folding results in bulk particle thickening.

239

240 **4.2. Particle-size distribution and morphological analysis**

241

242 The size of the collected gold particles ranges between 0.11 and 3.08 mm (Fig. 6). Mean values
243 and standard deviation (SD) for length (L), width (W) and thickness (T) are: 0.84 mm (0.56 mm), 0.52
244 mm (0.33 mm), 0.19 mm (0.12 mm), respectively. Morphological indexes return the following mean
245 values (SD): Cailleux flatness index CFI= 4.58 (3.62). Corey shape factor CSF= 0.35 (0.20). Mean
246 particle aspect ratio AR= 1.67 (0.52), and equivalent diameters ESD and ECD are: 0.66 mm (1.01 mm),
247 0.65 mm (0.41 mm), respectively. Histograms for the longest dimension (L) and the particle equivalent
248 diameter ESD, depicted a potential bimodal distribution, with peaks around L = 0.4-0.6 mm and 1.2-1.6
249 mm.

250 The lognormality of the length was assessed using a QQ-plot (fig. 7). Two deviations for the
251 diagonal are visible in the QQ-plot around 0.5 mm and 1.5 mm, which correspond to the mode peaks
252 found in the histogram of the figure 6. Based on these findings, an analysis of particle population mixing
253 was performed by Gaussian finite mixture modeling (mclust package; Scrucca, 2017). Applying the
254 Mclust function to the logarithm of length we obtained the optimal model of lognormal mixture of gold
255 particle populations. The best model has two lognormal populations with different standard deviation
256 (Table 1).

257

258 Regarding sphericity, the particles are subdiscoidal (31.2%), spherical (28.2%), elongated
259 (22.7%) and discoidal (17.9%). In terms of roundness, 41.6% were angular, followed by a 32%
260 intermediate and 26.40% rounded (Fig. 8 A). According to the particle classification diagram of Zingg
261 (1935), the predominant morphology of gold particles in the Fresnedoso creek is laminar (42.24%),
262 followed by discoidal (37.62%), spherical (10.23%) and cylindrical (9.90%) (Fig.: 8 B). Particle
263 dimensions (L , W , T) and morphological indexes (CFI, CSF) have been compared to their sphericity
264 (Fig. 9A) and roundness (Fig. 9B), defining four and three categories respectively (e.g. Barrios et al.,
265 2015).

266

267 Boxplots (Fig. 9) present a moderate dispersion with some general trends: a) large particle sizes
268 correlated with subdiscoidal (2) and discoidal (1) morphologies, while the small-sizes show elongated
269 (4) and spheroidal (3) ones; b) for the CFI it is observed that the largest median values corresponds to
270 the subdiscoidal particles, followed by the discoidal, elongated and spherical. c) The CSF shows a
271 reverse trend with the largest median values corresponding to spheroidal particles followed by the
272 elongated, subdiscoidal and discoidal (Fig. 9B).

273

274 If we take now the populations, P1 and P2, from the statistical model, and evaluate the shape
275 and textural features of the 95.4% of the particles within each one ($2 \times SD$; Table 1), we observe that
276 population P1 contains, predominantly, spheroidal (angular: 21%; intermediate: 22%; rounded: 10%),
277 and elongated (angular: 15%; intermediate: 10%) particles (Fig. 10). Meanwhile, P2 it is represented by
278 spheroidal (ca. 50%), elongated (ca. 20%) and subdiscoidal (>20%) particles. Besides, particles in P1
279 group clearly have a higher content of folded (83%), hammered (80%), fractured (91%) and enveloped
280 (92%) particles.

281

282 Cailleux's (CFI) and Shilo flattening indexes for P1 were: mean CFI= 5.1, CFI_{max} = 9.8 and mean
283 Shilo= 4.0 [2.9-8.8]. Calculations for P2 particles resulted in: mean CFI= 5.2, CFI_{max} = 9.8 and Shilo=
284 4.2 [2.9-8.8] (Fig. 11).

285

286 **4.3. Internal texture and chemical composition of gold particles**

287

288 Three types of gold can be distinguished based on color and textural features under the
289 petrographic microscope and SEM-EMPA investigations, correlating with chemical variations on
290 Au/Ag ratio. Image analysis has been used to estimate the volume fraction of each gold type.

291

292 **Gold type 1 (Au1):** shows a light-yellow color under the petrographic microscope and dark-gray with
293 backscattered electrons mode (BSE) under SEM-EMPA (Fig 12 A - D). It is the most abundant type

294 with an 88% of the particle areas, predominantly the core sectors. Inclusions of primary minerals such
295 as quartz, sulfide and sulfosalts were not found in the studied particles (Loen, 1994; Naden and Henney,
296 1995; White and Hedenquist, 1995; Barrios, 2014).

297

298 **Gold type 2 (Au2):** is pink in color under the petrographic microscope and light gray in BSE mode
299 (SEM and EMPA). It occupies between 0.2 and 5% of the area of the particle predominantly distributed
300 in the outer rim surrounding Au type 1 with a sharp boundary. Sometimes Au2 define bands up to 100
301 μm length x 15 μm width, probably corresponding to grain boundaries and/or healing microfractures
302 (Fig. 12 B, D and E).

303 **Gold type 3 (Au3):** The color is similar it to Au2, but it appears as very fine allotriomorphic grains (<10
304 μm ; Fig. 12 D), within a mixture of phyllosilicates and iron oxi-hydroxides. This mixture fills particle
305 gulfs and cracks close to the rim and locally inside the particles (sectioning effect) (Fig. 12 B, D and F).
306 The Au3 is always in sharp contact with Au2 defining interlobated boundaries toward the interior of the
307 particle. However is never found in contact with Au1.

308 Chemical analyses of gold particles indicate a correlation between gold types 1, 2 and 3, and a
309 progressive Au refinement. Besides, the higher the Ag content the lighter the color of the particle.
310 Quantitative analyses (EMPA) demonstrate that gold particles of the Fresnedoso creek are Au:Ag alloys
311 (e.g.: Hough et al. 2009), with intra- and intergrain variations in Au/Ag ratios (Fig. 13). This is coherent
312 with published data in Central Iberian Massif (Loen 1994; Barrios 2014). Table 2 shows the average
313 content of Au per particle in selected morphotypes. The most abundant gold type (Au1) has a
314 composition: $\text{Au}_{89-94}\text{Ag}_{11-6}$. Gold type 2 (Au2) has a high to very high purity, with a composition (Au2)
315 = $\text{Au}_{99}\text{Ag}_1$. The contrast of chemical composition between both gold types can be seen in Figures 12
316 and 14.

317 It has been impossible to analyze the chemical composition of gold type 3 (Au3), due to the very
318 fine grain-size and the presence of clay/oxi-hydroxides films. However, energy dispersive x-ray
319 spectroscopy (EDS) maps in Au2 and Au3 areas, suggest that the chemical composition of gold type 3
320 is similar to the Au2 highest purity values, a fact that correlates with it similar coloration (Fig. 12 E and
321 F, and Fig. 13). Moreover, in a companion research, gold type 3 has been identified and described in
322 particles and nuggets from nearby areas, such as Santibáñez el Alto, whose analysis confirm almost total
323 absence of Ag in its composition (Barrios, 2014).

324

325 Ideally core sector in particles preserve the most primitive compositional and textural signature
326 (e.g. Hough et al., 2009; Stewart et al., 2017). According to the Au-content and texture in the core of
327 the particle, three different groups of gold particles can be identified (Fig. 14): Group 1 (Gr 1), shows
328 the lowest Au-content, ranging from 89.21 to 87.28 Au wt% (Fig. 14 A and B). Group 2 (Gr 2), presents
329 the most refined gold, with values between 93.76 and 93.04 Au wt% (Fig. 14 C, D, E and F). The Group

330 3 (Gr 3) shows a very heterogeneous core region with values between 98.54 and 89.1 Au wt% (Fig. 15
331 A, B and C).

332

333 While particles in Gr 1 and 2 show a homogeneous and regular texture, those in Gr 3 depicts a
334 distinct high porosity (ca. 40.65%). Particles with high porosity are traditionally called spongiform
335 (Davies et al., 1989; Santosh and Omana, 1991; Craw, 1992; Krupp and Weiser, 1992; Eyles, 1995;
336 Kalinin et al., 2009; Reith et al., 2009). Image analysis shows a mean pore-size about 4.5 μm (Figs. 15
337 and 16). Porosity density is not homogeneous and Ag-content changes accordingly: the higher the
338 porosity, the lower the Ag-content (Fig. 15 A). Pores show a geometric pattern which remind triple-
339 point grain boundary junctions, which tentatively suggests a grain-size range between 6.5-2.5 μm (Fig.
340 16).

341

342 5. DISCUSSION

343

344 5.1. Morphotextural analysis and fluvial transport

345

346 Particle size distribution (L or ESD) indicates that, at least, two populations exist (Fig. 6). The
347 analysis of lognormality of L (QQ-plot; Fig. 7) supported the bimodal character, defining two modes
348 around $L = 540 \mu\text{m}$ and $1540 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The statistical analysis of mixture of lognormal
349 populations with mclust returned an optimal model of two populations (P1 and P2) with relative
350 proportion of: a) P1, 70% of particles with a mean (L) size of 540 (SD = 80) μm , and b) P2, 30% of
351 particles with mean (L) size of 1540 (SD = 410) μm . Several explanations may concur: 1) gold particles
352 come from a single primary source where different sizes coexisted, probably due to the overlapping of
353 several mineralization pulses, or the progressive exposure of distinct erosional levels, 2) there are two
354 separated sources, where different degree/distance of transport led to two distinct size-modes, 3) there
355 is a mixture of monocyclic and polycyclic populations, where particles derived from their first
356 sedimentary cycle, are mixed with sedimentary recycled gold particles (paleoplacer) (e.g. Giusti, 1986;
357 Knight et al., 1999a; Youngson and Craw, 1999). The morphological analysis of the particles contained
358 within $2 \cdot SD$ around the P1 and P2 modes shows that P1 particles have experienced higher mechanical
359 reworking (Hammering, folding...) than P2 ones. This fact could be interpreted as the result of longer
360 transport distance for P1 population (e.g. Tishchenko, 1981; Hérail et al., 1990; Youngson and Craw,
361 1993, 1995; Eyles, 1995; Youngson and Craw, 1999; Townley et al., 2003). On the other side, flattening
362 indexes for both populations depicted similar values, with mean $CFI \sim 5$ and $Shilo \sim 4$, reaching CFI_{max}
363 ~ 10 . It has to be noted that our selection is conservative as the size-range was truncated at 95.4%
364 ($2xSD$).

365

366 In addition, particle shape and roundness are characteristics used to interpret transport degree
367 and detect mixtures of sources. The Zingg (1935) morphological classification indicates that the
368 flattened morphologies (laminar + discoidal) are the most abundant (ca. 80%; Fig. 8). In contrast,
369 roundness remains low, with most of particles being angular (42%), and only 26% rounded. Several
370 studies in fluvial environments suggest that gold particle flattening and roundness tend to increase
371 quickly with the transport distance in river environments (Webster and Mann, 1984; Wilson, 1984;
372 Knight et al., 1999a; Hough et al., 2009). In our case, flatness and roundness depicts opposite trends.
373 This could be interpreted as the dominant laminar shape in our particles is a primary morphology.

374

375 The Cailleux's flattening index (CFI) is a morphological indicator of mass redistribution by
376 hammering during transport, but also provide information about particle dynamics in a flow (e.g. Shilo
377 and Shumilov, 1970). Our particles show mean CFI values ca. 5, what points to a low hammering effect
378 and, hence, low transport distance. Moreover, a relatively low CFI (< 7), tends to increase settling
379 velocity for small particles, promoting gold retention in the placer (Shilo and Shumilov 1970; Youngson
380 and Craw, 1999). These observations support the idea of a strong source morphological signature,
381 implying a relatively proximal character of the Fresnedoso placer (e.g. Barrios et al., 2015). In addition
382 to that, about 1% of particles shows $CFI > 10$ ($CFI_{max} = 22$; Fig. 9), a fact which is compatible with
383 particles transported by several kilometers (e.g. Loen, 1995; Hérail et al., 1989; Wierchowiec, 2002;
384 Youngson et al., 2002). Interestingly, the higher CFI values correspond to subdiscoidal, elongated and
385 cylindrical particles, appearing in all cases rounded. This suggests that those shapes travelled longer
386 distances (Youngson and Craw, 1993, 1995; Eyles, 1995; Wierchowiec, 2002; Barrios et al., 2015). The
387 interpretation of the Corey shape factor (CSF) is not straightforward since most of particles have CSF
388 values close to or below the lower bound ($CSF = 0.3$) defined by Corey (1949). In the case of spherical
389 particles mean $CSF \sim 0.45$ points to a relatively high sedimentation rate (Tourtelot, 1968; Le Roux,
390 1992; Crawford et al., 2007; Boekhout, 2012; McGrath et al., 2015).

391

392 Flatness, roundness and folding are fundamental parameters for describing the relationship
393 between morphology and transport distance (e.g. Hérail et al., 1990; Knight et al., 1994; Youngson and
394 Craw 1999; Barrios et al., 2015). The placer classification of Youngson and Craw (1999), based on
395 Lindgren (1928), Kartashov (1971) and Boyle (1979), distinguishes: first-cycle (primitive placers),
396 multicycle (recycled placers) and multisource placers (combination of primitive and recycled). Primitive
397 placers are typically developed along the high-gradient segment of the stream ($> 1^\circ$). Flattening and
398 folding of gold particles use to be absent, with very low $CFI = 1 - 3$ and $CFI_{max} < 7$ (e.g. Youngson and
399 Craw 1999; Barrios et al., 2015). On the contrary, placers developed along the trunk segment of the
400 stream (low-gradient parts $< 0.2^\circ$), are commonly multicycle and/or multisource placers. There,
401 flattening and folding are widespread, with $CFI_{max} > 45$. Transition zones between high and low-gradient

402 zones have been defined by the first finding of flattening/folding evidences in particles ($7 < CFI_{\max} <$
403 20) and a significant population of discoidal morphologies.

404

405 In our case, the Fresnedoso longitudinal profile (Fig. 17 A) shows a high-to-intermediate
406 gradient ($1.12 - 0.8^\circ$), which correlates with the transitional zones placers of Youngson and Craw (1999).
407 In addition to that, there are several evidences that point to a mixture of populations, both in sizes and
408 morphological types (multicycle/multisource). In those cases where a multicycle/multisource population
409 is suspected, it has been proposed that mean values of the flatness indexes (CFI, Shilo) are not usable
410 for transport/flatness estimations. In those cases, the index maximum is preferred as a better estimation
411 of the total transport distance, either as a result of a single or cumulative multiple cycles (recycled placer)
412 (e.g. Knight et al. 1999b). If we consider the whole set of particles in the Fresnedoso creek placer, the
413 $CFI_{\max} = 22$ ($Shilo_{\max} = 21$). Conversely, based on our conservative statistical model, populations P1
414 and P2 have $CFI_{\max} \sim 10$ ($Shilo_{\max} \sim 9$), with median CFI and Shilo values 20% higher in the case
415 of P1 population.

416

417 If we compare with published models (Fig. 18; Knight et al., 1999b) our results point to a wide
418 distance range to the source: 2.5 - 140 km (Fig. 18). Present and paleocurrent data support a regional
419 flow and sediment transport coming from the north (e.g. Bascones Alvira et al., 1987). Taken into
420 account the dimension of the Fresnedoso creek basin (ca. 10 km long) and other streams in the area, an
421 assuming the Distance/Shilo model of Knight et al. (1999b), the upper bound (140km) is probably not
422 realistic because a major drainage divide occurs ca. 60 km northward. Therefore the corresponding
423 flattening index ($Shilo = 21$) could be better interpreted as the result of cumulative work during several
424 sedimentary cycles. The results from statistical model show a consistent $Shilo_{\max} \sim 9$ which suggests a
425 maximum transport distance between 40 – 50 km (Fig. 18). It is interesting to note that primary deposits
426 exist, within that range in the hanging-wall of the Ponsul-Gata fault or even closer (20 km; Fig. 17 B).
427 They have been described as hydrothermal quartz dykes/veins hosted in slates of the Schists and
428 Greywacke Complex (SGC; Fig. 1), with Au-Arsenopyrite assemblages (Barrios, 2014). Those primary
429 lodes are common around the Moraleja and Coria basins (20 – 30 km), and probably many of them
430 remain unknown (Fig. 17 B). The primary laminar shape deduced from our morphological analysis
431 supports the existence of a proximal source, comprised of small veins, hosted in the SGC, between 2.5
432 - 10 km (P1 and P2, $Shilo_{\min} = 3$, mean $Shilo = 4$; Figs. 18 and 17 B). Besides, the role of the POG-fault
433 activity on the sedimentary evolution of the placer could be relevant exposing lower levels of the
434 hanging wall over time and needs to be evaluated in the future. As a preliminar conclusion, the
435 Fresnedoso creek gold deposit is a placer developed in the transition zone of the stream, in which single
436 and multicycle populations coexists, probably as the result of a paleoplacer recycling. The primary
437 source of the Fresnedoso placer is unknown, but the results point to a mixture of proximal and distal

438 sources, in the 2.5-10 and 20-50 km ranges respectively, hosted in the SGC (Figs. 17 and 18); this is
439 supported by the geology of the area.

440

441

442 **5.2. Compositional evolution of gold in the Fresnedoso placer: primary source(s) and secondary** 443 **processes**

444

445 The presence of a compositional zoning in alluvial gold particles are well known worldwide.
446 The combined analysis of chemical evolution and morphology is critical to decipher the formation of a
447 placer (Desborough, 1970; Giusti and Smith, 1984; Groen et al., 1990; Youngson and Craw, 1993;
448 Knight et al., 1999a; Townley et al., 2003; Chapman et al., 2000a, 2011; Chapman and Mortensen,
449 2016).

450

451 **5.2.1. Primary source(s)**

452

453 Our samples are simple bimetallic Au:Ag alloys. In particles core, volume composition range
454 between 5.87% and 12.32 Ag wt%. The presence of quartz inclusions and inter-growths, as well as
455 quartz molds in gold particles (Figs 3 and 4), together with textural features compatible with grain
456 boundaries (Figs. 12 D and 16), support the interpretation of core regions as relics of primary gold
457 (Ramdohr, 1965; Desborough et al., 1970; Antweiler and Campbell, 1977; Giusti and Smith, 1984;
458 Mann, 1984; Mosier et al 1989; Loen, 1995; Naden and Henney, 1995; Townley et al., 2003; White and
459 Hedenquist, 1995; Wierchowiec, 2002). In addition, archaeological evidences have demonstrated
460 Roman mining exploitation of primary gold in quartz veins, poor in in sulfides, hosted in the
461 precambrian Schist-Greywacke complex in the area (SGC; Figs. 1 and 17 B) (Barrios et al., 2010). The
462 Ag wt% range (fineness) is within the typical compositional interval for primary hypogenic gold (e.g.
463 Hough et al., 2009).

464

465 Compositional differences observed in the core of particles, (Gr 1= 10.79 - 1.72 Ag wt%; Gr 2=
466 6.24 - 6.96 Ag wt%; Gr 3= 10.9 - 1.46 Ag wt%; Figs. 14 and 15), could be reflecting: 1) different stages
467 of the primary gold mineralization (e.g. Giusti and Smith, 1984), 2) vertical or lateral chemical zoning
468 of a primary deposit (Chapman et al., 2000a; McCready et al., 2004; Townley et al., 2003), and/or 3)
469 multiple primary sources (e.g. Hérail et al., 1990). Silver content in our samples cores show a relative
470 narrow range (1.46-10.9 Ag wt%) compatible with those found in orogenic gold deposits (Morrison et
471 al., 1991; Ramsay et al., 1998; Tomkins, 2010). There are, however, some correlation with
472 morphotextural data that could clarify the processes. On the whole, Gr 1 particles comprise larger grain
473 size, mostly discoidal, rounded, with higher rate of broken, folded and hammered particles, with mean

474 CFI 5.53 and CSF 0.25, corresponding to the P2 population (Table 1). In contrast Gr 2 and Gr 3 particles
475 have smaller grain size, mostly spherical and angular, and with average CFI and CSF values of 4.45 and
476 0.35 respectively, fitting within the P1 population. Thus, the combination of chemical and
477 morphotextural features, assuming a simple relationship of shape parameters with transported distance
478 supports the existence of two primary sources (Youngson and Craw, 1999; Barrios et al., 2015; Barrios
479 et al., 2015): P1= Gr 2 + Gr 3 and P2 = Gr 2, respectively. Notwithstanding the particles from Gr 2 and
480 Gr 3 groups depict equivalent transport/morphological features their texture and composition differ.
481 They could be the result of secondary processes as will be elaborated below.

482

483 **5.2.2. Secondary processes**

484

485 Gold type 2 (Au 2) shows an extremely low Ag-content (97.5 - 99.8 wt% Au). Whether in
486 particle rims, fractures or/and grain boundaries (Figs. 12 and 14), this feature has been previously
487 described by other authors in the characterization of placer deposits (Youngson and Craw, 1993, 1995;
488 Eyles, 1995; Knight et al., 1999a; Butt, 2006; Chapman and Mortensen, 2006; Nesterenko and
489 Kolpakov, 2007; Barrios, 2014; Rivas et al., 2017). There is a relative consensus about the supergenic
490 origin of this refined gold (e.g. Giusti, 1986; MacDonald, 2007). Apart from nature, Au-rich rims have
491 been also identified in jewelry and processes appear to be secondary either way (Grimwade, 1999). This
492 type of gold (Au₂) is resistant to chemical alteration and potentially shields the core region from
493 alteration (Desborough, 1970; Giusti, 1986; Youngson and Craw, 1993, 1995; Eyles, 1995; Knight et al.,
494 1999a). On the other hand, Au₂-rims could record information about depositional environment and
495 transport dynamics (e.g. Wierchowiec, 2002).

496

497 Several mechanisms have been invoked to form Au-enriched rims. Neoformation - precipitation
498 of gold result in very high purity gold, equivalent to the Gold type 2 (e.g. Desborough et al., 1971;
499 Wilson, 1984; Webster and Mann, 1984; Stoffregen, 1986; Clough and Craw, 1989; Grant et al., 1991;
500 Bowell, 1992; Craw and Mackenzie, 1992; Santosh et al., 1992; Loen 1994; Southam 1998; Freyssinet
501 et al., 2005). However gold neoformation - precipitation requires specific conditions like a high Au-
502 concentration in water, high water salinity and a reducing environment (Desborough, 1970; Lawrance,
503 1988; Groen et al., 1990; Barrios, 2014); there is no evidence in the area supporting those conditions.
504 On the other hand, watercourses associated with secondary Au mineralizations, typically have < 20 ppb
505 Au in solution and Ag-content 2 to 100 times higher than Au (Chao, 1969). In our samples, Gold type 2
506 depicts very low variance (Table 2 and Fig. 13 B) what in terms of neoformation - precipitation could
507 be interpreted as a single event for all morphotypes. The absence of zoning, sedimentary inclusions
508 trapped within the rim and crystal faces (Groen et al., 1990; Barrios, 2014; Craw and Lilly, 2016; Stewart
509 et al., 2017), altogether discards neoformation-precipitation as the dominant Au 2 formation mechanism.

510

511 Microorganisms can precipitate Au through a recycling process of dissolution - precipitation in
512 shallow surface environments (e.g. Shuster et al., 2015, 2016; Melchiorre et al., 2018; Dunn et al., 2019;
513 Rea et al., 2019). In addition to the high purity of gold, biogeochemical processes in nature generate
514 biomatization structures, nanometric gold crystals (Reith et al., 2010; Shuster et al., 2016; Melchiorre et
515 al., 2018; Dunn et al., 2019), and bacterioform gold shapes at the interface gold-water (Watterson, 1994;
516 Southam et al 2009; Reith et al 2010; Melchiorre et al., 2018; Dunn et al., 2019; Rea et al., 2019).
517 Experiments report the formation of nanophase gold crystals, colloids and euhedral crystals when
518 bacteria are exposed to mobile Au complexes (Watterson et al., 1984; Fairbrother et al., 2013;
519 Melchiorre et al., 2018). Apart from the high fineness, our gold particles do not present additional
520 evidence supporting a biochemical origin of gold type 2. In addition, we observe that in some particles,
521 gold type 2 is not limited to the rim area, but progress inside the particle through grain boundaries or
522 microfractures (Figs. 12 and 14) a feature not compatible with known biomineralization processes.

523

524 However, the textures identified in the gold type 2 (Au₂) are best explained by an Ag-leaching
525 process (e.g Fisher, 1935; Desborough, 1970; Giusti and Smith, 1984; Mann, 1984; Stoffregen, 1986;
526 Colin et al., 1989; Knight and McTaggart, 1986, 1990; Michailidis, 1989; Hérail et al., 1990; McDonald,
527 1990; DiLabio, 1991; Krupp and Wesier, 1992; Knight et al., 1999a; Barrios, 2014). Ag is more mobile
528 than Au in supergene environments (Pitul'ko, 1976; Mann, 1984; Webster and Mann, 1984; Wilson,
529 1984; Barrios, 2014), showing a higher solubility in acidic chloride solutions (Boyle, 1979; Mann, 1984;
530 Barrios, 2014). Moreover, the chloride ion is very common in soils, derived from meteoric water or as
531 a weathering product of Cl-bearing minerals (e.g. biotite) (Kehew, 2001; Barrios, 2014).

532

533 Gold de-alloying progresses as Ag reacts with Cl⁻ in solution to form AgCl. Ag-leaching led to
534 a Au-enriched area and a porosity increase. Eventually spongiform texture could develop (e.g. Davies
535 et al., 1989; Grimm and Friedrich, 1990; Craw, 1992; Krupp and Weiser, 1992; Barrios, 2014). Ag-
536 leaching probably progress from the particle rim into the core when fast-paths exists (e.g. Grain
537 boundaries, fractures). Our observations suggest that internal microstructure, and probably deformation
538 state (e.g. Stewart et al., 2017; Melchiorre et al., 2018; Dunn et al., 2019) play an important role, opening
539 pipelines for fluids to dissolve Ag (e.g. Colin and Vieillard, 1991; Gray et al., 1992; Hough et al., 2007,
540 2009; Larizzatti et al., 2008; Barrios, 2014). This process results in net contacts between gold type 1
541 (primary) and type 2 (Fisher, 1945; Groen et al., 1990; Knight et al., 1999a; Barrios, 2014) without
542 compositional gradation from the core to the outer rims (Bowles, 1988; Naden, 1988; McCready et al.,
543 2004; Barrios, 2014).

544

545 In the Figure 19 a conceptual model is proposed, following a temporal sequence (t1-t4). Ideally,
546 de-alloying in a gold particle stops when a complete rim of pure Au is generated. This could be reached
547 by a cyclic combination of: A) Ag-leaching and porosity generation, whether in a soil or along a stream.

548 B) Mechanical compaction (e.g. hammering, folding, abrasion...) which seals the porous surface,
549 probably by mechanical smearing of pure gold (Au₂ e.g. Knight et al., 1999b; Petrovskaya and
550 Fastalovich, 1955). Stewart et al. (2017) have demonstrated that a dynamically recrystallized gold rim
551 is formed in particles due to the mechanical (cold-) work in the river load-bed. C) (Micro-) Fragile
552 threshold could be reached by cold-work accumulation during transport, resulting in work hardening
553 (e.g. Fischer-Bühner, 2005; Corti and Hollidays, 2010); this eventually generates (micro-) fractures (Fig.
554 5 and 14) and opens discontinuity planes, which potentially reactivate the de-alloying mechanism (e.g.
555 cavitation; Kassner and Hayes, 2003). This process is probably favored in the strongest terms of Au:Ag
556 alloys, higher Ag wt% (primary gold, Au₁) (Corti and Hollidays, 2010), and gold polycrystals with
557 small grain-size (Hall-Petch relation; Hall, 1954; Lo et al., 1979).

558

559 When the Ag-leaching process is not interrupted by the self-rim Au-enriched (Fig. 19 B),
560 dissolution of gold particle could progress (MacDonald, 2007) and originates the gold type 3 (Au₃). The
561 result is the formation of depressions that can be occupied by a mixture of very small gold particles, Fe-
562 oxi-hydroxides (Fe-OOH) and phyllosilicates (Loen, 1995; Barrios, 2014). It is unclear the detail
563 mechanisms that develop gold type 3. A possibility is that Au-leached from the gold-rich rim precipitates
564 again near the surface of the particles, being trapped by Fe-oxi-hydroxides (Fig. 15A). The chemical
565 reaction responsible for the neoformation of this gold would be the reduction reaction of AuCl⁴⁻ complex
566 (Mann, 1984; Freyssinet et al., 1989; Colin and Vieillard, 1991; Santosh and Omana, 1992; Barrios,
567 2014). Fe²⁺ does not reduce Ag chlorides because the reduction potential of Ag-AgCl is lower than that
568 of Fe²⁺-Fe³⁺, so Au re-precipitated from chloride complexes is of high fineness (Mann, 1984; Barrios,
569 2014). This combination of pure Au and Fe-oxi-hydroxides is very common in lateritic environments
570 (Colin et al., 1989; Mann, 1984; Michel, 1987; Davies et al., 1989) and has already been proposed for
571 similar gold morphotypes (Au₃) in other alluvial gold deposits in Iberia (Pérez-García et al., 2000;
572 Barrios, 2014). If the porosity on the rims of some particles is the result of Ag-leaching and other
573 accompanying elements (Knight et al., 1999a; Barrios, 2014), the result could be a spongiform porous
574 texture (Grimm and Friedrich, 1990; Krupp and Weiser, 1992; Knight et al., 1999a; Barrios, 2014) as
575 the one observed in Gr 3 particles (e.g. #6; Figs. 15 and 16).

576

577 Interestingly the analysis of gold particles in lateritic profiles show significant variations in
578 vertical both in chemical and morphotextural parameters, being interpreted as the result of differential
579 exposition of the particles to reactive solutions (e.g. Michel, 1987; Larizzatti et al., 2008). Based on this
580 idea, we can speculate compositional and textural differences between Gr 2 and Gr 3 particles were the
581 result of differential weathering in a laterite. The heterogeneous compositional profile of Gr 3 particles
582 (Fig. 12 C) and their porous texture, suggest a more intense alteration than Gr 2 particles. In the Figure
583 17 model (t1), Gr 2 and Gr 3 particles represent different erosive levels in the same laterite, explaining
584 their equivalent transport distance (distal source) and the production of gold particles with a variety of

585 compositions. On the other hand proximal sources, (Gr 1 particles) show less refined gold probably due
586 to a combination of lower residence time in the alterite, less reactive environment and direct erosion of
587 basement outcrops and transport modification (t2-t4, Fig 19).

588

589 CONCLUSION

590

591 The Fresnedoso creek gold placer has been investigated for the first time in terms of
592 morphological, textural a compositional evolution of gold particles.

593

594 Size and morphological attributes support mixing of two gold populations: P1 (70%) 540 µm
595 mean size, and P2 (30%) 1540 µm. Shape and flattening features indicate P2 is relatively proximal (2.5-
596 10 km), and P1, distal (20-50 km). A small fraction clearly shows evidences of polycyclic origin, so
597 recycling of paleoplacers (tertiary) has to be considered to some extent. Besides, laminar particles are
598 important with flatness and roundness showing opposite trends. This could be interpreted, as the
599 dominant laminar shape in our particles is a primary morphology. This is coherent with an undiscovered
600 primary source(s) in small-flat veins hosted in the metasediments of the Schist Greywacke Complex to
601 the North of the Ponsul-Gata fault.

602

603 All these features suggest the Fresnedoso creek gold placer is a deposit developed in the
604 transitional zone of Youngson and Craw (1999) with mono- and polycyclic particles. It is demonstrated
605 that the application of transport distance – Flattening indexes relationship (e.g. Knight et al 1999a) could
606 result in valid information as long as morphological analysis is conducted properly, even when the
607 number of data is limited. It is obvious that structural control on the Moraleja Basin sedimentary
608 evolution is important, e.g. affecting the drainage network, and/or exposing different erosion levels over
609 time, but more work is needed in the future to identify and quantify the tectonic imprint on gold-particles
610 population.

611

612 Compositional analysis of gold particle morphotypes has revealed that the Fresnedoso gold is a
613 Au:Ag bimetallic alloy, without any other inclusion. Three different compositional groups have been
614 defined after chemical analysis of particle cores: Gr 1 = 10.79 - 1.72 Ag wt%; Gr 2 = 6.24 - 6.96 Ag
615 wt%; and Gr 3 = 10.9 - 1.46 Ag wt%. These variations could reflect differences in primary composition,
616 spatial dispersion of sources or secondary processes. Altogether primary composition fits within the
617 range of orogenic gold deposits. Besides, it is an additional evidence of the mixture of populations in
618 the placer. In our case, Gr 1 correlates with P2 morphological group (proximal) and Gr 2 and 3 with P1
619 (distal). Particles from Gr 2 and Gr 3 are equivalent in terms of transport distance, but show textural and
620 compositional differences that could be attributed to differential weathering in a paleo-laterite.

621

622 Secondary processes modified the gold composition in the particles. In addition to the core (Au
623 type 1) and rim (Au type 2) textural zoning, reflecting primary and de-alloyed (Ag-leaching) gold types,
624 a third group (Au type 3) has been observed. The type 2 and 3 are very finesses gold (97.5 - 99.8 wt.%
625 Au), and represent two different evolutionary states: from initial Ag-leaching, at the rim and/or through
626 grain-boundaries and microfractures, to complete resetting of primary chemical imprint, pervasive
627 porous texture and Au re-precipitation with Fe-OOH and clays, respectively. A conceptual model is
628 proposed which combine, Ag de-alloying enhanced in a Cl-Fe rich environment (lateritic?) and the
629 deformation/recrystallization processes related to mechanical cold work in the load-bed during
630 transport.

631

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633

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644

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1006 **Figure and Table captions**

1007

1008 **Figure 1:** Geological map from the NE sector of the Ponsul-Moraleja basin (PM). Blue star indicates
1009 the sampling area along the Fresnedoso creek. The rose of directions of faults (inset) with a principal
1010 lineament around N48E and minor components ca. N120-130E. Dashed line represent mean POG trend.
1011 POG: Ponsul-Gata fault, MP: Messejana-Plasencia fault, (modified after Bascones Alvira et al., 1984;
1012 de Vicente et al., 2018).

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1014 **Figure 2:** Practical measurement of small gold particles placed on a glass-plate under the microscope
1015 (see the text for an explanation).

1016

1017 **Figure 3:** Examples of gold particles collected in the Fresnedoso creek gold placer. A) Large particles.
1018 B) Small particles. C) Example of an irregular particle, hammered and folded (SEM). D) A detail of the
1019 previous particle where several abrasion marks are recorded (SEM). Positive (E) and negative (F) planar
1020 surfaces, that could be interpreted, respectively, as gold crystal faces or molds left by minerals.

1021

1022 **Figure 4:** A) Particle subdiscoidal with spongiform surface; B) detail of the porous surface of the same
1023 particle in A); C) gold particle with the presence of filonian quartz;(SEM images). D) Scratches on the
1024 gold surface.

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1026 **Figure 5:** Selected micrographs of gold particles with hammering and folding features (A-F). Fractures
1027 as a result of severe hammering damage are evident in A), D) and F).

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1029 **Figure 6:** Histograms of particle dimensions (Length (L), Width (W) and Thickness (T); Equivalent
1030 diameters (ESD, ECD), and morphological indexes: Corey shape factor (CSF) and Cailleux flatness
1031 index (CFI). See the text for a discussion.

1032 **Figure 7:** QQ-plot for the logarithm of length (L) assessing the lognormality of length

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1034 **Figure 8:** A) Morphological classification of the particles according to Zingg (1935). B) Visual
1035 morphological classification diagram (Barrios et al., 2015).

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1037 **Figure 9:** Relationship of particle dimensions (L, W and T) and morphological indexes (CFI and CSF)
1038 with: A) Sphericity (1- subdiscoidal, 2- discoidal, 3- spherical, 4- elongated); B) Roundness (1- Angular,
1039 2- intermediate, 3- rounded) and their dimensions.

1040 **Figure 10:** Distribution of morphologies in size-groups P1 and P2, based on Barrios et al. (2015). See
1041 the text for a discussion.

1042 **Figure 11:** CFI distribution in particle-size populations P1 and P2.

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1044 **Figure 12:** Gold types based on color and textural features: A and B) Types Au1, Au2 and Au3. Note the
1045 sharp contact between Au1 and Au2 (petrographic microscope images). C and D) Gold type 2 forming
1046 rims both outside and within (triple-point grain boundary) (BSE-SEM images). E) and F) Gold type 3
1047 filling an elongated gulf. Allothriomorphic grains immersed in a matrix formed by clays and Fe-OOH
1048 (BSE-SEM images).

1049 **Figure 13:** AuAg alloy compositional range (EMPA) for representative gold particle
1050 morphotypes (particles #1 to 7; Figs. 14 and 15). A) Gold type 1 (Au1). B) Gold type 2 (Au2); C)
1051 Relationship between Au and Ag in particle 6.

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1053 **Figure 14:** Representative selection BSE (Back scattered electron) images of gold particles showing the
1054 Au wt% obtained by EMPA analyses. Taken into account the gold composition in the core region they
1055 are grouped in: Gr 1, (A y B) (particles 1 and 2); Gr 2 (C, D, E, F) (particles 3, 4, 5, 6 respectively). (See
1056 the text for an explanation).

1057

1058 **Figure 15:** Representative particle of Gr 3 (particle 7): A) Porous internal texture. Note porosity density
1059 is heterogeneous (SEM - BSE images). B) Enlarged region with ESD analysis (Au%) of high and low

1060 porosity areas. EDS elemental maps C) Au, and D) Ag from the same region. A thin rim is defined along
1061 the outer border in the particle, with a clear Au-enrichment. (See the text for a discussion).

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1063 **Figure 16:** Detail of the porosity texture in spongiform gold particles (particle 6; Fig 14. The area has a
1064 9 wt% Ag. Overlapped red lines highlight possible gold grain boundaries, with common triple-point
1065 junctions (white arrows). Estimated grain-size range between 6.5-2.5 μm . See the text for an explanation.
1066 (SEM image).

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1068 **Figure 17:** A) longitudinal profile of the Fresnedoso creek. F-F indicates the Ponsul-Gata (POG) fault-
1069 zone. FGP: Fresnedoso gold placer. B) Simplified map of the Moraleja basin and its surroundings, where
1070 principal gold deposits have been indicated (based on Sierra et al., 1975; Barrios, 2014). The distance
1071 to the FGP is indicated with concentric circles (Fresnedoso creek in red). Both POG hanging- and
1072 footwall areas present gold lodes (hydrothermal quartz - Au - arsenopyrite veins) within 20 -50 km
1073 range. Potential deposits, either primary or secondary ones, could be crops out in the short range to the
1074 north of the Fresnedoso creek placer. The principal trunk of the Rivera de Gata, Rivera de Acebo, Árrago
1075 and Traígas rivers are colored. The rose of directions obtained from drainage network show three
1076 principal lineaments N38E, N136E and N174E. The POG mean orientation (solid) and the principal
1077 orientation of the fracture network (dashed line; Fig. 1) are indicated, supporting a structural control of
1078 the drainage. See the text for a discussion.

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1080 **Figure 18:** Transport distance – flatness index (Shilo) relation based on Knight et al. (1999a)
1081 compilation. The solid black line describes the general trend of the Knight et al. (1999a) model which it
1082 is used here as a reference. Note that only $Shilo_{\text{max}}$, $Shilo_{\text{min}}$ and $Shilo_{\text{mean}}$ for size-populations (P1 and
1083 P2) have been considered from the Fresnedoso gold placer (FGP). Potential primary sources have been
1084 confirmed in a 20-40-50 km radial distance from the FGP. Taken into account the limitation of data our
1085 results fit the general model. (1) Hérail et al. (1989); (2) Knight et al. (1999a); (3) Tishchenko (1981,
1086 1992, from (2)). See the text for an explanation.

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1088 **Figure 19:** Conceptual model of chemical and textural evolution, of detrital gold particles in the
1089 Fresnedoso creek placer in different temporal stages: t1) liberation of primary gold particles (Au1) from
1090 two different sources: distal lateritic profile (L) and proximal quartz veins hosted in the Schists-
1091 Greywacke Complex. Note Gr 2 and Gr 3 particles may represent different erosive levels. t2) Initial
1092 incorporation of gold particles to a water stream, with a variable bed-load with silicates (Qtz: quartz)
1093 and rock fragments, a common ion in solution (Fe, Cl). (A) a simplified scheme of water-gold
1094 interaction, and the development of a finesses porous gold rim (Au2) due to Ag-leaching. Note that a
1095 limited dissolution-precipitation reaction of $\text{Au} + \text{FeOOH}$ is proposed as the origin of Au3. This process
1096 could be more pervasive in soil environments. t3) Mechanical cold work on particles and developing of

1097 a sealing rim of gold Au₂ (+Au₃?). In B) some potential mechanisms activated by the impact of strong
 1098 phases (Qtz) (e.g. Hammering damage) include: (R) recrystallization and grain size refinement in the
 1099 outer rim (e.g. Stewart et al., 2017), (S) gold smearing and, (C) cavitation activated along grain
 1100 boundaries and triple-point junctions. These led to the compaction and sealing of the particle core. C)
 1101 Deformation accommodation eventually resulted in work hardening and microfragile failure at different
 1102 scales. This could generate new paths for external fluids to progress deeper with Ag-leaching. In some
 1103 cases (e.g. longer residence times in soil, higher stream power, longer transport distances, or favorable
 1104 chemical environment) the evolution led to a complete textural and chemical reset of the particle (e.g.
 1105 spongiform particles). Note A, B, C processes could be coeval. (See the text for a discussion).

1106 **Table 1:** Results of the Gaussian finite mixture modeling. Mean, standard deviation and proportion of
 1107 the two populations are included.

1108 **Table 2:** Summary of chemical analyses of Gold type 1 (Au1) and type 2 (Au2).. N: number of analyses
 1109 per particle and gold type. SD(·): Standard deviation. #: particle number.

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1.- Discoid / Angular 2.- Subdiscoid / Angular 3.- Spheroid / Angular 4.- Elongated / Angular
 5.- Discoid / Intermediate 6.- Subdiscoid / Intermediate 7.- Spheroid / Intermediate 8.- Elongated / Intermediate
 9.- Discoid / Rounded 10.- Subdiscoid / Rounded 11.- Spheroid / Rounded 12.- Elongated / Rounded

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